

Risk of Bias Assessment Form

Blank PROBAST+AI-based form — one per included study

Project: Multimodal Artificial Intelligence for Acute Coronary Syndrome Detection: Protocol for a Systematic Review of Diagnostic Accuracy and Methodological Quality

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PROSPERO registration: CRD420261322905

Funding: European Union Horizon Europe MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowship, grant agreement No 101211169.

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This is the blank risk-of-bias form accompanying the registered protocol. It contains no completed assessments.

Study identifier: _____ **Reviewer:** _____ **Date:** _____

Instructions

PROBAST+AI is the primary appraisal tool, applied across its four domains (participants, predictors, outcome, analysis). Each domain verdict is derived from its feeder fields by the fixed combination rule shown. LEAKAGE_RISK and APPLICABILITY_CONCERN are assessed on separate axes; applicability does not contribute to the overall rating. ROB_OVERALL is derived last from the four domain verdicts. Two reviewers assess each study independently after a three-study calibration exercise; Cohen's kappa is computed for TIER_CATEGORY_TYPE, ROB_OVERALL, and LEAKAGE_RISK on a 20% sample (kappa < 0.60 triggers re-calibration). QUADAS-2 is applied as a secondary assessment to enable comparison with prior ACS reviews. Source Col # refers to the field number in the Data Extraction Instrument.

1. Leakage risk (LEAKAGE_RISK)

Target field: Col 62 — finalise after Cols 60/61 **Permitted values:** None / Possible / Likely / NR

Feeder field	Source Col #	Signalling question
UNIT_OF_ANALYSIS	12	Is a patient-level train/test split confirmed?
MODEL_TYPE	28	Feature selection before the split, or test-set tuning?
MISSING_DATA_METHOD	60	Imputation performed before the split?
CLASS_IMBALANCE_METHOD	61	Resampling performed before the split?
Incorporation bias	15	Is a label criterion also a model input? (Yes → Likely)

Combination rule: Any feeder Likely → Likely; else any Possible → Possible; else None.

Verdict: None Possible Likely NR

Reasoning (one line for the manuscript): _____

2. Participants (ROB_PARTICIPANTS)

Target field: Col 64 — scope: detection = ED or prehospital first contact **Permitted values:** Low / High / Unclear

Feeder field	Source Col #	Signalling question
SETTING	5	Representative first-contact population (ED/prehospital in scope)?
STUDY_DESIGN	7	Consecutive/random enrolment vs case-control enrichment?

Combination rule: Any feeder High → High; else all Low → Low; else Unclear.

Verdict: Low High Unclear

Reasoning (one line for the manuscript): _____

3. Predictors (ROB_PREDICTORS)

Target field: Col 65 Permitted values: Low / High / Unclear

Feeder field	Source Col #	Signalling question
OUTCOME_BLIENDED	18	Was the predictor recorder influenced by knowing the outcome?
STUDY_DESIGN	7	Retrospective: immutable records with separate adjudication?

Combination rule: Any feeder High → High; else all Low → Low; else Unclear.

Verdict: Low High Unclear

Reasoning (one line for the manuscript): _____

4. Outcome (ROB_OUTCOME)

Target field: Col 66 — finalised after Section 2 Permitted values: Low / High / Unclear

Feeder field	Source Col #	Signalling question
Incorporation bias	15 / 17 / 19–22	Is the reference-standard criterion also a model input (complete or partial)?
OUTCOME_BLIENDED	18	Were adjudicators blinded to the model inputs?

Combination rule: Incorporation bias = Yes → High (and LEAKAGE Likely, dual-flag); else based on OUTCOME_BLIENDED.

Verdict: Low High Unclear

Reasoning (one line for the manuscript): _____

5. Analysis (ROB_ANALYSIS)

Target field: Col 67 — finalise after Cols 28/30/47/60/61 Permitted values: Low / High / Unclear

Feeder field	Source Col #	Signalling question
MODEL_TYPE	28	Post-hoc selection or training-AUC-only reporting?
SAMPLE_SIZE_ADEQUACY	30	EPV < 10?
CALIBRATION_REPORTED	47	Formal calibration reported? (absence = minor concern)
MISSING_DATA_METHOD	60	Missing-data handling described and justified?
CLASS_IMBALANCE_METHOD	61	Resampling leakage?

Combination rule: Any confirmed flaw → High; borderline / calibration-only → Unclear; none → Low.

Verdict: Low High Unclear

Reasoning (one line for the manuscript): _____

6. Overall risk of bias (ROB_OVERALL)

Target field: Col 63 — derived last

Combination rule: Read the four domain verdicts: any High → High; else any Unclear → Moderate; else (all Low) Low.

Verdict: Low Moderate High

Reasoning: _____

7. Applicability concern (APPLICABILITY_CONCERN)

Target field: Col 68 — separate axis; does not affect ROB_OVERALL Permitted values: Low / High / Unclear

Feeder field	Source Col #	Signalling question
SETTING	5	ED or prehospital first contact? (downstream settings → High)
INTENDED_USE	14	Is the stated purpose a detection task?
PREDICTOR_TIMEPOINT	32	Predictor timing mismatched to the intended use?
OUTCOME_DEFINITION	16	Does the outcome match the detection question?

Combination rule: Any dimension High → High; else any Unclear → Unclear; else Low.

Verdict: Low High Unclear

Reasoning (one line for the manuscript): _____